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Review Article

**REVIEW STUDY: METFORMIN AND TYPE 2 DM
PREVENTION**

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Background: Metformin is considered as the main antidiabetic medicine which has been appeared to improve anticipation of T2DM patients as an essential end-point for prevention of diabetes.

Objective: This study aimed at providing an update on the effect of metformin in prevention of T2DM.

Methods: The online medical database was searched then the English articles from 2009 – 2020 were included in the review.

Results: There were 36 studies involved concentrating on the prevention effect of metformin on type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Conclusion: many studies propose that metformin is an active, tolerable, cheap, and cost-saving interference that can inhibit or prevent development of diabetes. Most of the metformin studies showed that metformin is not used in real-world settings. Thus, metformin needs more evidence-based treatment studies among high risk patients to evaluate its advantage in prevention or delay of diabetes and assessing its side effects and long-term effects.

Keywords: metformin, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), prevention, delay, prediabetes.

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BACKGROUND:

Further than 30 million adults in U.S. are suffering from type 2 diabetes and it's associated with high health care costs approaching 20% of healthcare spending[1, 2]. In spite of the latest decreases in quotes of diabetes-related problems and consequences, the excessive incidence of kind 2 diabetes is a considerable social complications[1]. Also, prediabetes is considered as an intermediate metabolic problem between diabetes and normal glycemic state and it can include either impaired tolerance of glucose (IGT), fasting glucose (IFG), or both situations. The hazard of development to diabetes is higher among people with impaired glucose tolerance and fasting glucose approaching the diagnostic levels of diabetes. Approximately 15% to 30% of adults suffering from prediabetes are predicted to develop diabetes within five years[3].

Metformin was set up as a first-line of treatment for treatment of T2DM in light of the fact that it goals insulin opposition and hyperinsulinemia and satisfies the treatment objectives including controlling the glycemic state and decreasing the cardiometabolic hazard [4]. It is considered as the main antidiabetic medicine which has been appeared to improve anticipation of T2DM patients as an essential end-point for prevention of diabetes [5].

Metformin is one of the primary restorative choices in polycystic ovary disorder (PCOS) and is associated with insulin opposition and hyperinsulinemia characterizing higher rate of metabolic states and expanded cardiovascular risks[6]. Studies have demonstrated that metformin can lessen the occurrence of T2DM and CVD incidence among people with impaired fasting blood glucose and hindered glucose resilience [7]. Metformin can be used for the treatment of high-chance people with weakened glucose resilience and disabled fasting blood glucose [8]. Also, it was suggested that metformin can be used for avoidance of T2DM in people with prediabetes regardless of way of life mediation [9].

The subjects that benefitted the most are those with higher baseline fasting glucose or HbA1c and women with a history of GDM [10]. Considering the protective cardiometabolic effects of metformin beyond glycemic control, research and clinical interest have focused at its effect in persons with normal glucose tolerance (NGT) and MS, who are at a high-risk of T2DM and CVD[11].

Metformin has been appeared to diminish the improvement of T2DM for about 15 years[10]. It also has a defensive cardiometabolic impacts of metformin outside glycemic ability to control

among a high-danger of T2DM and CVD subjects[12, 13]. This review efforts to accumulate evidence about the potential preventive effects of metformin in T2DM development.

METHOD:

The online information was searched using key words including metformin, prevention, T2DM then the articles were evaluated then all the eligible English studies from 2010-2020 included in the present study.

RESULTS:

The study included 36 articles were included in this review that were published between 2009-2020 including RCTs, reviews, case-controlled studies and clinical trials.

- Uses of metformin as antihyperglycemic agent:

Many studies have shown that metformin acts essentially by improving the activity of insulin in the liver to diminish the pace of production of the hepatic glucose levels[14]. Upgrades in insulin activity in skeletal muscle additionally add to the restorative activities of metformin. Together, these activities decrease blood glucose in the setting of hyperglycemia with almost no potential for initiating hypoglycemia[15].

Metformin has an antihyperglycemic effect but not a hypoglycemic effect as it can decrease fasting blood glucose level after 1 year of treatment but it doesn't show an effect on the postprandial plasma glucose level[16]. Also, it was found to have the ability to decrease the fasting blood sugar levels among obese, overweight and metabolic syndrome subjects within one year of treatment with life-style modifications with no significant change in postprandial plasma glucose levels[11]. However, the shorter periods of treatments less than 3 month showed no effect on the fasting blood glucose levels[17]. Thus, metformin can reduce the high insulin and high blood glucose levels without affecting the secretion of insulin by improving peripheral and hepatic sensitivity of insulin. Metformin can inhibit the gluconeogenesis and production of glucose in liver and also rise the uptake and usage of glucose in peripheral tissues [18].

- Metformin for insulin resistance:

Many studies have reviewed the effect of metformin usage for insulin resistance and hyperinsulinemia reduction in different populations from different regions of the world with no effect of the dosage of the duration on its anti-hyperinsulinemia effect. independently of the duration of the study and the dose of metformin used.

Insulin resistance is related to higher hazard of developing T2DM and cardiovascular diseases. The best marker of insulin opposition in non-diabetic people is fasting hyperinsulinemia. It is viewed as a fundamental necessity of the MS characterized as insulin opposition condition [19].

Prevention of T2DM requires treatment targeted at both insulin secretion and insulin resistance. Treatment of insulin resistance is promising as a strategy to prevent the development of T2DM and CVD in high-risk subjects. Thus, agents that ameliorate insulin resistance and reduce hyperinsulinemia, such as metformin, may provide a therapeutic option of the MS and could prevent T2DM and CVD [20].

Deterrence of T2DM necessitates treatment focused at both insulin discharge and insulin resistance. Treatment of insulin obstruction is hopeful procedure to forestall the initiation of T2DM and CVD in high-hazard populations. Metformin can give a restorative alternative of the MS and could forestall T2DM[11].

In addition to the decrease in fasting blood glucose level some studies showed a significant decrease in the 1 and 2 hours PGL insulin levels after longer periods of treatments (1-2 years)[6, 21].

- Prevention of T2DM:

Ongoing examinations firmly propose that metformin is viable, especially among subgroups of higher-risk subjects [22, 23]. Additionally, metformin use was related to a decrease in diabetes development running from 4.4% to 14.3% and a number expected to treat somewhere in the range of seven and 14 over a period of 3 years[23]. This information likewise show that metformin is protected, practical, and potentially even cost sparing. Nonetheless, late evaluations show that metformin is once in a while utilized in certifiable settings, featuring a significant hole that necessities further study[24-26]. Along these lines, extra investigations recognizing clear genuine models for qualification for metformin use for diabetes avoidance might be useful in translating which patients ought to be considered for metformin therapy[27].

Studies exhibited that metformin use might be advantageous in subsets of the patients who are at higher danger of development of diabetes[28]. Studies of treatment impacts show critical heterogeneity including obese subjects, higher fasting glucose levels, and gestational diabetes history were supposed to have more serious decrease with metformin[29-31]. So also, there were a significant decrease in the hazard of developing diabetes among 25% of DPP members

with using metformin. In this way, there is proof to recommend that metformin utilize would be sensible to consider in specific subsets of patients with prediabetes at higher hazard[32].

Indeed, even among higher hazard patients who ought to use metformin, the safety protocols may likewise be a hindrance as common reactions were identified with metformin integrating a gentle gastrointestinal impacts and deficiency in nutrient B12[33]. To relieve against these symptoms, the dose of metformin can be used slowly with considering the routine testing of nutrient B12[34].58, Also, concentrated way of life programs must be fortified as first line treatment for all patients with prediabetes[35].

Furthermore, Metformin was compared with diet and exercise to prevent or diminish the danger of T2DM in individuals at expanded hazard for the improvement of T2DM. The blend of metformin and concentrated eating routine and exercise contrasted with escalated diet and exercise just neither indicated a bit of leeway or detriment in regards to the improvement of T2DM [36]. However, most of the studies were not real-world studies.

CONCLUSION:

In this literature review, many studies propose that metformin is an active, tolerable, cheap, and cost-saving interference that can inhibit or prevent development of diabetes. Most of the metformin studies showed that metformin is not used in real-world settings. Thus, metformin needs more evidence-based treatment studies among high risk patients to evaluate its advantage in prevention or delay of diabetes and assessing its side effects and long-term effects.

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